
In search of new management skills for adaptation to modern organizational challenges: the leaders of the XXI century

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Abstract

The main method of the research is a view of some key publications available spots of expertise in leadership and human resource management and other references and their short presentation in the article with two main goals –their distinct indication and their supplementation of each other in the management matters. The method of the research of the article is also a comparative analysis and differences of interpretation by the court and their application in practice. The materials analysed are in the following key areas: management; organizational behavior; leadership; motivation and esc. Analytical materials and websites of public institutions have also been used, with proven good practices in the field of leadership.

Key words: leadership, human resource management, model 3P, adaptation, changes.

Introduction

Every organization should strive to be more flexible, dynamic, and easily adaptable to successful practices in the field of human resource management and leadership, but a number of objective and subjective assumptions inhibit these processes. This is due to the reach of the changes that have occurred in the public and the crisis situations that the world is currently experiencing. The improvement of professionalism in human resource management through the use of effective management practices, by optimizing the organizational-functional model of work, the requirement of systemic knowledge in human resource management and leadership and skill development for use of modern management tools, as well as indication of the various management tools, have all played outstanding roles in the development of leadership skills in recent years.

The current paper examines these fresh difficulties and makes an effort to draw the reader's attention to these trends and patterns.

The 3P Model of Leadership, written by Ranjay Gulati, aims to add relevant elements to current management difficulties. It is a new and currently little-known theory of leadership.

Results and Discussion

Leadership cannot be a constant in a world that is constantly changing. Improvement is necessary with changes, and this is what keeps the best performers at the top.

It is crucial to create leaders who will set an excellent example for others around them by outlining the path they should take. In this way, people will indirectly come to understand the distinction between managers who manage to administer and managers who manage to motivate.

An organization's culture of openness and trust is a necessary condition for the development of informal groups, which, in the absence of a formal leader, could elevate their informal leader to lead. This absence results in team distrust, disloyal relationships, meanness, jealousy, posturing, level differences, etc. (Ashkenas, R., A. McDougall 2014). Globalization, industrialization, and urbanization have triggered climate change, emissions, and pollution (Gigauri, I., V. Vasilev 2022). Employee resistance to teamwork or supervisors' lack of interest in the environment in which

employees operate could be the cause of a potential absence of a trusting and welcoming environment (Perry, L., J. & L. Wice 1990). If managers engage each employee individually and get to know their unique demands, the workplace will become a more desirable place for professional growth. The environment must be carefully studied and analyzed in these activities. The strength of the influence of the factors of the environmental conditions, which are considered to be extreme, has increased. The complex of influences of the factors of the external and internal environment, which require active actions, is defined as extreme situations (Borissov, T. 2022, p. 17). Additionally, it will inspire them. Managers frequently claim that they maintain employee motivation through personal involvement and commitment, collegiality, the promotion of manifested, a variety of rewards, friendly interactions, material stimulation, access to information, open contacts, showing faith in a positive outcome, etc. Only the most fundamental social requirements of the employee may be met by the mentioned benefits. That is the biggest challenge – to instrumentalise the leadership and deliberative practices efficiently so that the decisions taken to be considered rational, legitimate, and protecting fundamental human and other rights of all affected who will feel respected and committed to their implementation (Chankova, D., V. Vasilev 2020, p. 218). The need for the expression of other motivating factors, such as future confidence, a need for respect, and self-realization, is present. Higher motivation will have an impact on managers' attitudes toward the professional advancement of employees' careers, which are clearly not at a good enough level when referring to the outcomes of their responses.

In search of new solutions for effective leadership

Responses to the question about the preferred leadership style (democratic, liberal, or authoritarian) identified the democratic type as the most popular. However, there are also many who argue that the combination of a liberal and authoritarian style indicates the existence of managers who are incapable or unable to adapt to present and future changes due to their outmoded beliefs or negligence of duty. Such leaders have no place in organizations operating in the present day. Only democratic leaders can give the flexibility, empowerment, and shared power that are required. They are leaders.

Changes that occur often reliably predict flexibility and openness to the novel and new innovations.

Another painful issue has come to light with the advancement of information technologies and their integration into organizations' operations: the challenges associated with using them. A significant portion of employees and entire organizations had to deal with the impressively quick growth of computer technology before the necessity for extra training in computer literacy in more complicated components.

Effective horizontal and vertical communications are a must for improving the working environment in a company. Communicating with internal audiences is of key importance to the success of the organization. Communication has an important role to play in motivating, building trust, creating common identities, and strengthening employees' sense of responsibility (Vasilev, V., V. Arabadjieva 2020, p. 02). They also grow through dialogue. However, they should also be viewed as a tool for spreading leadership and authority across the business, not just as a means of exchanging information. Another little but significant difference. It is encouraged by a positive workplace environment, and new technology makes it easier.

If we consider how we may identify the signs of leadership, we will come to the conclusion that they can appear in a variety of ways and disguises (Vasilev, V. & D. Stefanova 2021, p. 29). However, he will always be expected to contribute insightful suggestions for how the company might grow, to decide on a course of action and what objectives should be met, and to exert influence for the organization's growth in the appropriate direction (Icheva, M., V. Vasilev 2021, p. 916). Undoubtedly, the public sector needs fresh thinking and ideas to address the problems the environment presents to the security system as a whole. The public sector needs to be innovative since state management is so crucial. Due to its significance for state policy, it is of primary importance. But it's insufficient on its own. Striking for the proper actions and providing practical

remedies is insufficient. In order to implement them, organizational capacity creation is required. The current system of the extensive bureaucracy, with its centralized regulations and excessive regulation of state officials, failed. It is costly, wasteful, and it makes it harder to solve problems. It's time to clean up the "mess" that authoritarian governance has created over the years. The state government's following democratic reformations failed to quickly identify the best strategy for moving management from centralized to decentralized. In general, training and professional development programs will be increasingly perceived and will play an important role in setting new values and achieving the desired changes in organizational culture in the age of globalization. Integrating staff training and professional development with organizations, strategies is also seen as a new type of challenge (Stoykov, S., V. Vasilev 2021, p. 18). Giving leaders the authority to act, entrusting leadership to adaptable, open-to-change organizations, institutions, and departments, hiring and training qualified and motivated staff members and giving them the chance to contribute fresh ideas, and involving citizens in the public sector's work are all necessary in order to find a solution. These objectives are basic, clear, and important, but it will not be simple to attain them. The bureaucracy must be reduced in order to increase the public sector's responsiveness to change. The path is followed by getting rid of extraneous management levels. A public sector that is always learning must be established. Employees' personal and professional growth is encouraged by the introduction of pay based on performance, rather than duration of service in a particular position. The next step in transforming the public sector is to encourage communication between staff and management and remove obstacles to effective leadership in public administration. These are just a few essential conditions to meet while looking for novel approaches to leadership development. How to strike the right balance between allowing people to act freely and maintaining control over them is one of the major issues that many CEOs and leaders face (<https://www.novavizia.com/model-3p-za-liderstvo-na-gulati> – last visited 11.01.23). On the one hand, managers should provide their staff members some level of independence. On the other hand, order and discipline are necessary for an organization to succeed.

The so-called "3P Model of Leadership", which enables leaders to more accurately achieve the balance required to guide their subordinates in the proper direction, stands out among the new theories about leadership that we examined. In the essay "Structure That's Not Stifling" for the Harvard Business Review in 2018, Ranjay Gulati, a professor of business administration at Harvard Business School in the United States, presents the 3P model of leadership. Gulati's model has two components:

- *Freedom*: refers to how much decision-making and action-taking authority employees have at work.
- *Control*: How much operational monitoring and discipline are used by the organization.

Employee freedom is connected with the trust that is placed in them to think and act independently of the organization's name. Empowerment has been demonstrated to be crucial for improving empathy, internal motivation, innovations, and work outcomes (<https://www.forbes.com/sites/stevedenning/2022/11/25/ranjay-gulati-how-deep-purpose-drives-extraordinary-performance/?sh=62daee766bd3> – last visited 21.01.2023). Giving people total freedom, or working with no supervision, can be harmful, ineffective, and impracticable. It is simple for issues to develop when there is no control of any type, such as a lack of discipline and attention, decreased quality, and missed deadlines. Gulati believes that freedom and control are not concepts that must be opposed to one another and may even coexist. In order to do this, he suggests a model with three components that executives should implement in their businesses in order to ease the conflict between freedom (empowerment) and control (discipline). The following components are included in the Gulati leadership 3P model:

- Purpose
- Priorities
- Principles

Since all three elements start with the English letter “P”, that is where the and comes from 3P model name. The 3P model of leadership's first component is purpose, according to Gulati (<https://deppurpose.net> – last visited 22.01.2023). The term “purpose” in this context refers to a single, overarching objective, the organization's mission, the reason for its existence, or, as it is more popular to say these days, her “Why?” The purpose of the organization will provide direction and give work done by employees a sense of purpose, so it is crucial that the leader inspires and motivates all of their associates to share this (<https://hbr.org/2019/07/the-soul-of-a-start-up> – last visited 22.01.2023).

The second component of Gulati's three-part leadership approach is priorities. Here, “priorities” refers to core values and significant social norms that guide individual behavior within the organization. When the organization's main strategies and interests are clear, it is simpler for employees to act in agreement with them and, yes, to concentrate their time and effort on the most crucial tasks. Critical success factors, key efficiency indicators, and management by objectives are just a few examples of items that a business could consider to be priorities. The organization's main priorities must be explained to all of its members in a clear and specific manner by the leader if they are to receive the appropriate framework of discipline in their behavior at work.

Gulati's 3P model of leadership has principles as its third component. A straightforward set of rules should be developed by management to control employees' everyday behavior based on the organization's goals and priorities (<https://hbr.org/2021/05/why-todays-startups-pursue-both-ideas-and-ideals?ab=seriesnav-bigidea> – last visited 22.01.2023). Principles can be restrictions on what people cannot do as well as guiding principles about what they should do. It is crucial that the principles are not overly detailed since doing so would harm the effectiveness of employee empowerment, but they should also not be too general because doing so would weaken effective control (<https://www.degruyter.com/downloadpdf/j/nispa.2015.8.issue-2/nispa-2015-0010/nispa-2015-0010.pdf> – last visited 22.01.2023).

Gulati emphasizes the importance of constant and effective communication between a leader and his subordinates in order to use the 3P model for leadership (<https://findingmastery.net/ranjay-gulati/> – last visited 22.01.2023). The organization's goals, priorities, and guiding principles should be communicated and explained by the leader on the one hand. On the other side, the leader needs to encourage followers to provide feedback on the three components-purpose, priorities, and principles. The 3P model, which is the foundation for productive work through a healthy balance between freedom and control, can only be understood by the leader and his collaborators in this way – through two-way communication. The necessity for a proper balance between employee freedom and control, which makes the model practical in contemporary organizations, can be summed up as follows: by employing the 3P model, managers can deal more successfully with one of the major difficulties in organizations.

Conclusions

The world we live in is constantly changing, so leadership cannot be considered a constant. Changes call for progress, which is what maintains the best performers at the top. The relationships between the ruler and the ruled, or between supervisor and subordinate, are particularly significant and delicate. These connections could be clear to see or they might not. However, they have a direct impact on the organization's operations. That is why the socio-psychologically generated environment is crucial for the productive operation of the company and the organization's head, acting in his position as a leader. The development of positive relationships within a group, as it undoubtedly is within an organization, is influenced by many variables, the most crucial of which are the qualities of the leader and his capacity to establish, maintain, and strengthen a positive working environment, as well as his capacity to inspire, motivate, and build trust among the people he supervises.

And in this context, a number of new theories and models give valuable answers, one of which was discussed in the work at hand with the concept that it is unquestionably appropriate to every modern organization.

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